

THEORETICAL RESEARCH ON THE EVOLUTION OF JOB EVALUATION METHODS

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Abstract

Purpose – The paper aims to make an x-ray of the ways of approaching the job evaluation process during the last century. Job evaluation is an essential component of human resource management, but at the same time it is responsible for determining the value of a job in an organization. Job evaluation is based on the types of activities necessary to perform the tasks of a job or by extrapolating, the work/labor type and work/labor value associated with a job.

Methodology/approach - The paper starting point consists in the review of the main types of job evaluation methods, as currently defined and accepted. Once the current concepts are established, we will move on to the second stage of the paper, which will consist of analyzing the original approaches to work/labor management in the meanings defined by Taylor and Bedeaux. This analysis aims to identify concepts similar to those used in job evaluation.

Findings – The paper has two objectives: a) to draw similarities between the methods of work/labor evaluation proposed by Taylor and Bedeaux and the methods of job evaluation; b) applicability verification of the working hypothesis based on the use of work/labor evaluation as a reference for selecting the most objective methods of job evaluation.

Research limitations/implications – One of the research limitations is the fact that in the specialized literature there is no general consensus regarding the classification and content of job evaluation methods.

Practical implications – Identifying correlations between work/labor evaluation methods and job evaluation methods, will create the premises for determine ways for identifying those job evaluation methods that offer the highest levels of objectivity

Originality/value – Using the work/labor evaluation methods developed by Taylor and Bedeaux as references in selecting the most objective job evaluation methods.

Key words: work evaluation, labor evaluation, job evaluation.

Introduction

Job evaluation is an essential part of human resource management, and in the same time it is responsible for determining the value of a job in an organization. Job evaluation is generally based on the types of activities necessary to perform the tasks of a job, the working environment, the personal skills of the job incumbent and the importance of the work. The paper starting point consists in the review of the main types of job evaluation methods, as currently defined and accepted. Once some fundamental concepts are established, we will move on to the next part of the paper, which will consist in analyzing the approaches to work and labor management in the meanings defined by Taylor and Bedeaux. This analysis aims to identify concepts similar to those used in job evaluation.

Current approaches to job evaluation

Job evaluation is a key activity in human resources. The role of human resources management is to connect employees with the desired results of the work performed to achieve the objectives of the

organization. Increasing the organizational efficiency of a company depends on various external and internal factors, and job evaluation can be the aspect that favors the company's chances in front of the competition (Adamus, 2009). Job evaluation is a process mainly used by large civil or governmental organizations. Kahya (2006) estimated that half of U.S. positions in the U.S. were the subject of the evaluation process.

In practice, job evaluation is a systematic process that aims to establish the relative value of jobs in an organization by developing a framework on which to base pay decisions. The same idea was highlighted by Eargle (1972), job evaluation is a complete procedure for determining the value of a job in relation to other positions in the organization. The job evaluation thus provides a necessary reference for maintaining and defining a fair wage structure based on two solid coordinates: making coherent decisions on wage levels and ensuring equal pay for work of equal value (Armstrong, 2003, p. 569).

Spyridakos et al. (2001) show that job evaluation includes comparative processes, because it is necessary to explain the relationships and interdependencies between jobs. This is done through an analysis of the roles, objectives and achievements of each position. It should be noted that job evaluation is distinct from the evaluation of the employee as a person, but of the skills he must have to occupy or fulfill that position (Mathis, Nica, & Rusu, 1997, p. 203).

In conclusion, from a practical-conceptual point of view, the main aims and objectives of the job evaluation are:

- to compare the duties and responsibilities of a post with another post;
- to achieve the hierarchy and placement of positions in an organization by establishing the degrees of importance for each position (Eargle, 1972, p. 2);
- to ensure the premises for fair remuneration based on the value of the work performed;
- eliminate bias and discrimination of any type of reward system work Mathis (1997, p. 203);
- to provide employees with a favorable climate for efficient activity by confirming that their work matters to the organization and that it is objectively appreciated.

From the point of view of the phases of job evaluation procedure, the following sequence can be identified, according to figure 1.

Fig. 1. Job evaluation process. An adaptation after (Heneman, 2003, p. 12)

Although job evaluation methods have been developed since the beginning of the twentieth century, there is no general consensus in the literature on their types of classification. For example, Chang & Kleiner (2002) nominates only 4 methods of job evaluation: job ranking, job classification, score-based

evaluation and factor comparison along with their possible combinations. On the other hand, Armstrong (2003) suggests the following general categories:

- non-analytical methods (job ranking, job predetermined grading, benchmarking);
- analytical methods (numerical job evaluation, factor comparison);
- methods based on a single factor;
- methods based on skills or competences;
- methods based on market pricing;
- methods developed by consulting firms in the field (Hay).

Eargle (1972) details the job evaluation methods used by the National Electrical Manufacturers Association (NEMA). They are based on the numerical job evaluation and the factor comparison method. The only non-analytical methods mentioned are job ranking and the job predetermined grading. In order to determine the hourly wages, the numerical job evaluation and factor comparison are used as working examples. From this point of view, it can be concluded that the desideratum of obtaining and using an objective foundation in the evaluation of positions can be obtained starting from these two evaluation methods.

In addition to the methods mentioned, Heneman (2003) also introduces methods for assessing competency-based positions. Thus, competencies are defined as an accumulation of knowledge, qualifications, skills and other personal attributes necessary to achieve the performance standards of the position. Competences are also defined as observable behavioral elements that manifest as a result of having the qualifications, skills and knowledge necessary to meet the requirements of the job (e.g. teamwork).

For an organization that aims to achieve medium and long-term performance and profit goals, it is necessary that all its resources be directed as efficiently as possible in this direction. From the point of view of human resources, it is necessary to achieve a harmonious internal climate conducive to obtaining the best results. It is important for employees that their work is important, that it is appreciated and evaluated correctly and fairly. In terms of working methods used, job evaluation is based on non-analytical methods such as job classification, ranking or benchmarking that would ensure rapid and inexpensive assessments, but in the medium and long term, due to the lack of quantifiable and measurable criteria they can create dissatisfaction among all categories of staff and arouse suspicion of biased assessments.

In the case of analytical methods, such as numerical job evaluation or the Hay method, the company is required to allocate significant resources of time and specialized staff to perform evaluations. But these methods, once completed, will outline not only simple job profiles, but a coherent and objective vision of the structure of the human component, credible, accessible and widely understood among employees and shareholders.

Working principles used in work evaluation

The analysis of the work is based on the foundations created by Frederick Winslow Taylor (1856 - 1915), who was also nicknamed "the father of scientific management". He stated that the study of time is the most important component of scientific management. In his works "Shop Management (1903)" and "Concrete Costs (1912)", the study of time is based on time units. However, during his lifetime, few British managers understood the importance of time units and were even less able to develop a time unit system that could be used in practice.

Taylor's work "Principles of Scientific Management (1911)" has been described as the most influential book in the field of organizational theory in the twentieth century, being also Taylor's most important work. Time units represent the time required to perform basic or unitary operations as part of a worker's work. Thus, the manager has the task of dividing the work into units, more precisely into irreducible elements or operations. The division and timing of work would allow managers to compile an index of standard periods for each work activity. Such an approach to work leads Renold (1918) to say that scientific management is management itself.

However, the introduction and use of scientific management methods is conditioned by at least 2 factors:

1. the existence of a well-trained and qualified staff;
2. precise definition of the various activity types and equipment produced.

Taylor believed in transferring control from workers to management. He set out to increase the distinction between mental (planning work) and manual labor (executing work). Detailed plans, specifying the job and how it was to be done, were to be formulated by management and communicated to the workers (Rinehart, J.W., 1975, p.44). By 1912, in the United States, Taylor's system was used by at least 50,000 workers, whose results multiplied by at least 300 percent. One 1917 US study estimated that there were 169 scientifically managed plants in the USA, and this was very high compared to Britain (4), Canada (4), France (5), Japan (6) and Russia (9). Germany, Spain and Italy possessed no scientifically managed plants.

While Britain and the US were at war, a system explicitly based on Taylor's *unit-times* was being developed by a young engineer named Charles E. Bedaux, who had not only noticed Taylor's point but also that others had missed it. The system designed by Bedaux was first used in 1917 by a furniture factory - Imperial Furniture Company in Grand Rapids, which for 2 years tried unsuccessfully to implement Taylor's time units. The system proposed by Bedaux is different from Taylor's because Taylor set time rules for certain operations in order to frame them in the working hours of the workers, while Bedaux proposes the introduction of energy units of the worker workforce.

The system is based on a points system corresponding to each productive minute. A working day of 9 hours is considered by Bedaux to consist of 540 minutes with 40 minutes allowed for interruptions, the workers being thus obliged to perform 500 work points. Each activity corresponds to specific Bedaux scores and if workers get higher scores than needed daily, then they receive a bonus. Points associate predetermined tasks with their standard completion times and are then summed to obtain the required daily values. The standard values of the points are multiplied by a coefficient of rest - *r* or delay - *d*, which takes into account the time lost with fatigue or inevitable delays. Standard durations plus percentages for rest and delays provide the standard that is expected of an ordinary worker under normal working conditions. Bedaux stated that the score he proposed together with the coefficients *r*, *d* are the attributes that make his system different. The principle of the work intensity measurement system is based on the aggregation of effort and breaks in a unit, the share of breaks being given by the intensity of physical and/or mental demands from the effort made. Another interesting feature of the system is that Bedaux came up with the idea of measuring including times not assessed by the system, periods such as maintenance or overtime, called not on Bedaux time, NOB. Conceptually, Bedaux stated that "efficiency does not necessarily mean high production, but it is about maximizing the production of a worker taking into account the available facilities." In April 1921, the points became Bs and also in that period he began to use the *work measurement* as a concept.

Between 1926 and 1939, in the United Kingdom a number of 178 organizations in various fields and industries used the Bedaux system, and among the most important customers were Kodak, Gillette, General Electric. The positive effects of the introduction and use of the Bedaux system for 15 industrial fields were manifested as follows:

- labor costs reduction: 17 ÷ 40 percent;
- increase worker productivity: 33 ÷ 185 percent;
- increasing the company's revenues: 7% ÷ 25 percent.

As with the introduction of Taylor's system, the introduction of labor intensity measurement has caused industrial strife, downtime and strikes in Europe and North America.

Job evaluation and work evaluation – parallels and crossing points

This section aims to achieve the two objectives of the paper: a) to draw similarities between the methods of work/labor evaluation proposed by Taylor and Bedaux and the methods of job evaluation; b) applicability verification of the working hypothesis based on the use of work/labor evaluation as a reference for selecting the most objective methods of job evaluation.

Table 1 summarizes the main features of job and work evaluation procedures.

Table 1. Characteristics of job evaluation and work evaluation methods.
An adaptation after (Adamus, 2009)

Crt. no.	Method name	Characteristics	Advantages	Disadvantages
1.	Job ranking	A simple method based on ranking jobs from the most complex to the most simple.	- easy to implement and use; - easily understood by the employees.	- it uses no definition for a model; - has no accuracy; - does not measure the complexity of a job.
2.	Factor comparison	An analytical method based on determining the job posts hierarchy regardless of job difficulty.	- easy to implement and use; - easily understood by the employees.	- subjectivity implied in analyzing the job; - does not create any job description; - does not measure the complexity of a job.
3.	Numerical job evaluation	An analytical method based on determining the level of job difficulty giving a numerical number to every job factor and then summing them in order to obtain a value in points for every job.	- easy in evaluating and describing the differences between post; - takes into account more factors responsible for influencing the difficulty level of a job; - offers the evaluator defined evaluation criteria; - provides a flexible relation between work and remuneration.	- difficult to implement; - it requires a thorough knowledge about post and tasks; - establishing the factor points implies a degree of subjectivity
4.	Hay method	An analytical point method based on four factors: know-how, problem solving, accountability and work environment.	- a method constantly adjusted and modified by the consultants of Hay Group based on the experience from over 40 countries worldwide.	- difficult to explain to employees.
5.	Market pricing	A method based on evaluation of pay rates in comparison with the market pay rates for similar job posts.	- the job is paid as much as the market is willing to pay.	- it does not take into account the fact that values of posts in one organization may differ from other from other organization; - difficult to acquire information about pay rates in the market.
6.	Taylor method	An analytical method based on the division of activities into irreducible tasks evaluated in units of time.	- the division of activities into irreducible tasks created the premises for work efficiency	- laborious; - it requires a thorough knowledge about post and tasks;
7.	Bedaux method	An analytical method based on measuring work intensity.	- takes into account the work capacity of the worker depending on the activity performed; - divides a working day into standard work units needed to be achieved.	- laborious; - it requires a thorough knowledge about post and tasks;

Analyzing the data introduced in Table 1, it can be seen that the methods of labor evaluation due to their numerical nature are similar to the analytical methods of job evaluation. This is because non-analytical methods do not use a definition or model of evaluated work, nor do they measure the complexity of work. By reverse analogy, analytical methods of job evaluation are related to methods of work evaluation, as both approaches aim to measure the complexity and value of work. But this merit for both approaches comes with the price of using a very concise definitions of the evaluated work and with an in-depth knowledge of each job and the final product resulting from the work. From the point of view of the second objective of the paper, the work evaluation has matured and been completed by the approach of Charles Bedaux. This is because Taylor's time units do not take into account the conditions of the worker's effort. In contrast, the units of work intensity proposed by Bedaux take into account both

the physical effort and/or the intellectual effort involved in an activity or work. Thus, by considering the physical and/or intellectual effort, the confirmation is obtained that the analytical methods for job evaluation are those that take into account factors and sub-factors such as: working conditions (environment, temperature), physical effort (working position, driving weights), intellectual effort (numerical calculation skills).

Conclusions

The paper reviewed the main types of job evaluation methods presenting the advantages and disadvantages of each type. Then conducted an analysis of the work evaluation methods implemented by Frederick Winslow Taylor and Charles Bedaux.

The two objectives of the paper were achieved by identifying similarities between work evaluation methods and job evaluation methods, respectively confirming the working hypothesis that the most objective job evaluation methods can be based on the approach of Charles Bedaux who uses units to measure the intensity of workers' effort.

Future research aims to identify additional ways to increase the objectivity of job evaluation, such as using combinations between the numerical job evaluation method and the factor comparison method.

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